

Induced mutation and selection of High Yielding Strain of *Micrococcus glutamicus* for glutamic acid production

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Abstract : The objective of this investigation was to develop a new auxotrophic mutant from a regulatory mutant and to examine its potency for L-glutamic acid production. A high L-glutamic acid yielding strain *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ was developed from a regulatory mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁ by subsequent mutagenic treatments with ethyleneimine solution and UV rays respectively. *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁ was treated with ethyleneimine solution, the auxotrophic mutants isolated show varied pattern of extracellular amino acids. Seventy auxotrophic strains were obtained, out of which only twenty seven excreted 0.5–3.0 mg, L-glutamic acid per ml and all auxotrophs require biotin for growth and production of amino acid. Sixteen auxotrophs produced 1.0–2.5 mg, L-glutamic acid per ml and these auxotrophs required amino acids for their growth. Other auxotrophs lost their excretion capacity in subsequent fermentation trials. Further mutation of the biotin requiring auxotroph *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀ with UV rays resulted in the isolation of seventy seven auxotrophic strains out of which only thirty excreted L-glutamic acid (up to 6.25 mg/ml) higher than the parent auxotroph.

Keywords : Auxotrophic mutant, regulatory mutant, *Micrococcus glutamicus*, mutagenic, ethyleneimine, UV rays, amino acids, L-glutamic acid.

Introduction

The fermentative production of amino acids started in the fifties (1956-57) with the discovery of L-glutamic acid producing bacteria by Japanese Scientists^{1,2}. Since then most of the development work was devoted to the improvement of mutant strains involving classical and modern microbial genetics³⁻⁵ while efficiency of commercial L-glutamic acid production has steadily increased by the isolation of highly producing mutant strains. Microorganism employed in microbial production of amino acids are divided into 4 classes, including the wild type, auxotrophic mutant, regulatory mutant, and auxotrophic regulatory mutant strains^{3,6,7}. Mutant auxotrophic or resistant to some chemicals of *Micrococcus glutamicus* or *Brevibacterium* sp. are employed for L-glutamic acid production⁸⁻¹⁰. Process improvement for producing large amounts of L-glutamic acid using microorganisms remains a continual attempt⁶, where as the continuous development of superior strains imparted with properties advantageous for the commercial production of L-glutamic acid:

Selected mutant strains with improved productivity characteristics are used today in industries for the production of L-glutamic acid, which are obtained by various mutagenic treatments^{11,13}.

Monosodium glutamate (MSG), the single largest amino acid product has been used as a flavor enhancer throughout the world for the past fifty years. There are many applications of L-glutamic acid and its derivatives as surfactant, especially due to its lack of harmful effects to skin and their smooth appearance, it is much favored by cosmetic, moist containing and hair shampoo product manufacturers. L-Glutamic acid has got some pharmaceutical applications also¹⁰. Thus the demand for L-glutamic acid in different industries is fast expanding. In order to meet the demand of L-glutamic acid, three procedures for their production have been proposed : (i) protein hydrolysis, (ii) chemical synthesis and (iii) microbial production. However, microbial production of L-glutamic acid has got one advantage over other methods. In fact, the amino acid produced by this method is natural

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i.e. L-form¹⁰. Numerous investigators have reported on fermentation production of L-glutamic acid. Considering the economic importance of L-glutamic acid and superiority of the microbial production of this amino acid, our major aim of this study is to develop a new auxotrophic high L-glutamic acid yielding mutant strain of *Micrococcus glutamicus* from a regulatory mutant which can be used for large scale production of L-glutamic acid by fermentation process using indigenous raw materials available in our country especially from the stand point of saving production cost so that we can meet the industrial demands for L-glutamic acid.

Process improvement for production of large scale L-glutamic acid using the microorganism remains continuous attempt⁹. However, the continuous development of superior strains imparted with properties advantageous for the commercial production of L-glutamic acid. Selected mutant strains with improved productivity characteristics are used today in the industries for the production of L-glutamic acid, which are obtained by various methods including mutagenesis using both chemical and physical mutagens^{5,6,14} which is already proved to be the most effective method for the development of high yielding strain¹⁰. So, in our present study ethyleneimine as chemical and UV irradiation as physical mutagens have been chosen for the development of high L-glutamic acid yielding auxotrophic mutant from a regulatory mutant by induced mutation.

Materials and methods :

Microorganism : *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁, a regulatory mutant and the auxotrophic mutants derived from it were used in this study. The strains were maintained on Nutrient Agar Medium. Subculturing was carried out once in an every three weeks and the culture was stored at 4 °C.

The following media were used :

Complete medium (CM) : glucose, 1%; peptone, 0.5%; beef extract, 0.3%; yeast extract, 0.1%; pH 7.2 (before sterilization).

Medium for glutamic acid production : glucose, 10%; urea, 0.8%; K₂HPO₄, 0.1%; MgSO₄.7H₂O, 0.025%; yeast extract, 0.2%; pH 7.0.

Minimal medium (MM) : glucose, 2%; urea, 0.2%; K₂HPO₄, 0.1%; MgSO₄.7H₂O, 0.025%; biotin, 0.5 mg/ml; pH 7.2. Solution of glucose was sterilized before mixing. This medium was used throughout the mutation study.

Treatment with ethyleneimine : cell suspension (1 ml containing 10⁶ cells) was added to 9 ml ethyleneimine solution of different concentrations prepared from a stock solution having concentration of 500 mmol/ml resulting in dilution of ethyleneimine to 1 : 3000 (166.67 mmol/ml), 1 : 5000 (100 mmol/ml) and 1 : 7000 (71.43 mmol/ml). After a certain period of incubation (Table 1), 1 ml of sample was diluted in water in each case. The diluted bacterial cells were then plated on CD agar medium and kept at 28 °C for 2 days to develop discrete colonies. After proper growth, the colonies were transferred to yeast extract agar slants and stored at 4 °C.

Treatment with UV rays : 2 ml of the bacterial suspension containing 10⁶ cells/ml were taken in a Petri dish (5 cm diameter) and exposed to UV rays from a distance of 12 cm from different periods of time (Table 2). The source of radiation was a Hanovia germicidal lamp (15 watt). The treated *Micrococcus glutamicus* cells were incubated at 28 °C for 48 h and selected colonies were transferred to yeast extract agar slants and stored at 4 °C.

The cells selected from different stages of treatment with mutagens (ethyleneimine and UV rays) were finally tested for glutamic acid production by surface culture fermentation process.

Analysis of amino acids : Descending paper chromatography was employed for the detection of L-glutamic acid in culture broth and was run for 16–18 h on Whatman No. 1 filter paper. Solvent system used include *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water (2 : 1 : 1). The spots were visualized by spraying with a solution of 0.2% ninhydrin in acetone and qualitative estimation of L-glutamic acid in the suspension was done using colorimetric estimation method^{15,16}.

Results and discussion

Effect of ethyleneimine concentration :

A comparative study has been made on the survival of bacterial cells of *Micrococcus glutamicus*. Fig. 1 shows that ethyleneimine solution at a concentration of 1 : 3000 had greater killing effect where as concentration 1 : 5000 gave moderate effect. The maximum development of productive variant occurred when the period of treatment with the mutagen at a dilution of 1 : 5000 was 30 min giving the survival % of 0.3 (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Survival of *M. glutamicus* AB₁₀, obtained by treatment with different dilutions of ethyleneimine and development of productive variants at different intervals of time : (O) 1 : 7000 dilutions, (●) 1 : 5000 dilutions, (▲) 1 : 3000 dilutions and (Δ) represents development of productive variants for treatment with 1 : 5000 dilutions.

The distribution of the productive variants of the treatment has been given in Fig. 2. The development of auxotrophic glutamic acid producing variants showed a maximum and then decline, while non glutamic acid producing variants showed an increasing pattern even up to 60

Fig. 2. Distribution of productive variants obtained by ethyleneimine treatment : (Δ) glutamic acid non-producing variant, (O) glutamic acid producing variant and (●) zero variants.

min. Thus, we have isolated 226 strains after the treatment of ethyleneimine at different dilutions which include L-glutamic acid producing variants, glutamic acid non producing variants and zero variants, among which seventy auxotrophic isolated were tested for L-glutamic acid production. *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀ exhibited highest L-glutamic acid production capacity in fermentation medium (3.0 mg/ml). The production of parent strain *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁ (a regulatory mutant) was 0.7 mg/ml.

Table 1 shows the types of auxotrophs and the amino acid accumulation by the mutants obtained in the medium under condition of ethyleneimine treatment. The parent organism excreted on the average 0.7 mg of glutamic acid per ml in FM broth after 3 days of incubation in shake flask culture. The auxotrophic mutants exhibited varied patterns of extracellular amino acids. A number of them (14.2%) maintained the parental pattern of excretion and about 17.1% excreted less glutamic acid. Two new amino acids, viz. lysine and methionine, were found to be excreted by the other auxotrophs screened. Out of 70 auxotrophs, 27 excreted 0.5–0.3 mg glutamic acid per ml and all of them required vitamins for growth and amino acid accumulation²² auxotrophs produced lysine and 21 produced methionine. They also required vitamins for their growth and amino acid accumulation.

The excretion capacity of the mutants was maintained constant in subsequent repeated mutation trials. Auxotrophs are classified as required yeast extract, amino acids and vitamins.

Effect of UV treatments :

The bacterial suspension of *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀ was them treated with UV rays (15 watt) for differ-

Table 1. Relation between nutritional requirements of auxotroph obtained by treatment of *Micrococcus glutamicus* with ethyleneimine and their amino acid accumulation

Ethyleneimine	Exposure time (min)	Total No. of auxotrophs	Extracellular amino acid pattern				Requirement		Vitamins		
			Similar to parents	More than parents	Less than parents	Lysine	Methionine	Yeast extract		Amino acids	
1 : 3000	10	16	4	2	5	5	3	1	5	16	1
1 : 5000	30	25	4	2	3	7	6	2	7	25	2
1 : 7000	60	29	2	1	4	10	12	3	4	29	2

r, Frequency of spontaneous reversion × 10³.

ent periods of time (Table 2). The scoring of survivor and productive variants has been depicted in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. The scoring of survivors (Δ) and productive variants (●) obtained by treatment with UV rays.

Complete inactivation of cells took place in 1 h. Productive variants were detected only upon treatment for half an hour and then the number decreased with increasing period of exposure.

A maximum of 18 productive variants were obtained on exposure to UV rays for 30 min. After different period of treatment with UV rays 30 isolates were selected for glutamic acid production (Table 2). It was observed that the mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ exhibited the highest glutamic acid (6.25 mg/ml) production capacity in fermentation medium. This strain was studied to standardize the cultural conditions for the medium.

The mutational study showed that the mutagenic effect of ethyleneimine and UV rays on *Micrococcus glutamicus* have been well distinguished from the nature of survival curve. Both the mutagens showed a sharp killing effect.

A total 147 productive strains were obtained and studied in the present work. It was observed that ethyleneimine treatment produced 38.5% productive variants. UV irradiation resulted in the fermentation of 38.9% productive variants (auxotrophic mutants) which comprised 0.4% more productive variants.

Both the mutagens altered the base so that a new base pair appeared in daughter cells in a later generation which might adversely or favorably affect glutamic acid production¹²⁻¹⁴.

In the present study we have observed the superiority of UV rays irradiation for the development of high glutamic acid yielding auxotrophs of *Micrococcus glutamicus* whereas treatment with ethyleneimine favors the development of lysine and methionine producing auxotrophs.

In our study we have seen that the regulatory mutant (i.e. *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁) produced only 0.7 mg/ml L-glutamic acid. Mutagenic treatment of this strain with a chemical mutagen (i.e. ethyleneimine) developed another mutant strain. *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀ which produced even only 3 mg/ml L-glutamic acid. But further development of a biotin required auxotrophic, high L-glutamic acid producing mutant strain *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ which can produce L-glutamic acid upto 6.25 mg/ml in the present condition of fermentation. So, the mutagenic treatment developed a high L-glutamic acid yielding mutant strain of *Micrococcus glutamicus* from a low L-glutamic acid producing regulatory mutant. The newly developed strain can be used for large scale industrial production of L-glutamic acid using indigenous raw materials available in India. However, an attempt to scale up the fermentation process is under way.

Table 2. Relation between nutritional requirements of auxotrophic obtained by exposure of *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀ to UV rays and then amino acid accumulation

Period of exposure C to UV rays (min)	Total No. of auxotrophs	Extracellular amino acid pattern								r
		Glutamic acid			Other amino acids		Requirement			
		Similar to parents	More than parents	Less than parents	Lysine	Methionine	Yeast extract	Amino acids	Vitamins	
10	8	1	2	2	2	1	-	3	8	-
15	10	2	6	2	-	-	3	2	10	1
20	16	3	3	4	3	3	9	3	16	2
30	18	3	8	4	2	1	11	5	18	3
40	16	-	5	6	2	3	7	4	16	1
60	9	-	6	1	-	2	5	2	9	-

r, Frequency of spontaneous reversion $\times 10^3$.

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References

1. K. Miyai, T. Osawa and T. Suroo, Jap Pat, 39-2988/1964.
2. F. Yoshinaga, K. Kikuchi, T. Tsuchida and S. Okumura, Jap Pat, 51-44196/1976.
3. R. Katsumata, T. Mizukami and T. Oka, US Pat, 495441/1990.
4. S. Kinoshita, 'Recent Prog. Microbiol. 1963, Symp. Int. Congr. Microbiol.', 1962, 8, 317.
5. S. Komastubara, M. Kisumi and I. Chibata, Proc. Annu. Meet. Soc. Fermet. Technol., Jpn., 1973, 98.
6. K. Yamada, S. Kinoshita, T. Tsunoda and K. Aida, Kodansha, Tokyo, 1972.
7. O. Zelder, C. Klopprogge, H. Schoner, S. Hafner, B. Kroger, P. Kiefer and E. Heinzle, W00509139AZ/2005.
8. K. Kubota, K. Kageyama, I. Maeyashiki, K. Tamada and S. Okumura, *J. Gen. Appl. Microbiol.*, 1973, 19, 339.
9. S. Ozaki, K. Kono, S. Okumura, H. Okada and K. Sakaguchi, *Proc. Symp. Amino Acid Ferment.*, 1960, 2, 4.
10. S. Yamashita, H. Hoshi and T. Inagaki, in : "Fermentation Advances", ed. D. Perlman, Academic Press, New York, 1969, 444.
11. P. D. Lawley, *Progr. Nucleic Acid Res. Mol. Biol.*, 1966, 5, 89.
12. D. R. Krieg, *Progr. Nucleic Acid Res. Mol. Biol.*, 1963, 2, 125.
13. E. M. Witkin, Proc. XII Int. Congr. Genet. Tokyo, 1968, Sci. Council Japan, Tokyo, 1969, 3, 225.
14. E. Freese, "Molecular Genetics", ed. J. H. Taylor, Part 1, 207, Academic Press, New York, 1963.
15. F. P. Chinard, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1952, 199, 91.
16. J. R. Spies, *Methods in Enzymology*, 1957, 3, 468.

